

IMPLEMENTING FAMILY CORNER ACTIVITIES IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10827404>

Abstract. *This research will report on the implementing family engagement activities to involve parents in education which is aimed at practical implication for adults mostly to engage them in observing, assisting and learning with students using “family corner” activities. The article will provide research-based practices for family/community engagement and sociocultural findings in learning English language.*

Keywords: *family engagement, language learning, adult education, family corner, identity, community engagement.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqot ota-onalar va oilani yosh til o'rganuvchilar ta'limiga jalb qilish bo'yicha mashg'ulotlarni amalga tadbiiq qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu esa yoshi kattalarni "oila burchagi" singari mashg'ulotlaridan foydalangan holda o'quvchilarni nazorat qilish, ularga beriglan vazifalarda yordam berish va o'quvchilar bilan birgalikda til o'rganishga jalb qilishdan iboratdir. Maqolada ingliz tilini o'rganishda oila/jamiyat ishtiroki va ijtimoiy-madaniy tadqiqotlarga asoslangan ilmiy izlanish xulosalari taqdim etiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *o'quvchi ta'limida oila ishtiroki, til o'rganish, kattalar ta'limi, oila burchagi, o'ziga xoslik, jamoatchilik ishtiroki.*

Аннотация. *Данное исследование включает в себя реализацию образовательной деятельности по вовлечению родителей и семей в обучение учеников, изучающих иностранный язык. Это заключается в вовлечения взрослых для наблюдения за успешностью учащимися, помощи им в выполнении домашних задач и вовлечения их в изучение языка вместе с учащимися с использованием таких упражнений, как «семейный уголок». В статье представлены результаты исследований, основанных на участии семьи/сообщества и социокультурных исследованиях в изучении английского языка.*

Ключевые слова: *вовлечение семьи, изучение языка, образование взрослых, семейный уголок, идентичность, вовлечение общества.*

Beginning the primary education can be a challenging time for young learners, as they have to adapt to a more structured environment, start to read and write in their mother tongue, and begin to learn in a more formal way. This article shares our experiences using Family involvement in teaching and learning foreign languages. In the textbook that we designed together with colleagues “English Grade 1”, we acknowledge that help of family members and guardians are crucial motivating factor for students. It is known that family involvement in language learning has been widely researched and recognized as a crucial factor in children's language development and academic success. Dr. Kuhl's research on early language development emphasizes the importance of social interaction and language exposure in the family environment. Her studies, such as those on the social brain and the critical period for language learning, highlight how parental involvement and language-rich interactions shape children's language acquisition processes [Kuhl, 2004]. Therefore, we used a special activity after homework called as “Family Time!”. In this activity, students should discuss, learn and play with their family members or guardians. This exercise helps students not only build good relationship with their family members or guardians

but also they can monitor the learning process. The paper will report on implementing ways of engaging family members and guardians in education. Multiple activities will be provided that we have found to be successful. These activities help bridge family engagement while also supporting language development. As Dr. Catherine Snow states in her research on family literacy practices underscores the importance of incorporating literacy activities into family routines. Reading together, storytelling, and engaging in language-rich conversations at home contribute to children's literacy skills and language proficiency [Snow, 2019]. The "English Grade 1" educational-methodical complex is our first English language textbook written after the introduction of the National Curriculum covering grades 1-11 in the school education system of Uzbekistan. The National Curriculum aims to prepare students for life based on the standard-based education system. It brought many approaches to the educational system of Uzbekistan. One of them was the involvement of methods of engaging family members and guardians in education. According to Dr. Epstein's (2009) research on school and family partnerships emphasizes the significance of collaboration between families and educators in supporting children's academic success. Her framework for school-family-community partnerships recognizes the role of families as essential stakeholders in children's learning and underscores the importance of involving families in language learning activities. During the National Curriculum training, the concept of "family corner" was used for the first time in interactive activities. Implementing family corner activities in language learning can be a fun and effective way to engage the whole family/guardians in language practice. We used some ideas in our "Family time" activities like language games, storytelling, language-based crafts and projects, and using technologies to engage family members/guardians in the language learning process. The implementation of the new section “Family corner” helped us to find the cultural values and beliefs of Uzbekistan. We covered the number of sociocultural aspects such as language development, cultural understanding, intergenerational transmission, sense of identity, family bonding, and community engagement in our “corner”.

Moreover, implementing family corner activities in language learning can be an effective way to engage learners of all ages and create an immersive language environment at home. Here are some ideas for incorporating family corner activities into language learning that we used in our textbook:

- Asking and answering set of questions based on the topics of the lessons. Family members ask students ready questions related to the topics discussed in the lesson.
- Drawing pictures and having simple conversations about them. Students draw and colour the pictures and family members asks certain questions about these pictures.
- Arts and crafts activities that involve language learning. Students create themed art projects based on vocabulary words or cultural elements related to the target language and have conversation using them with family members.
- Setting family language challenges and rewards. Students and family members set language learning goals and challenges and celebrate achievements together.

For example:

Lesson 1. Who is in your family? Family Time!	Lesson 2. Who is this? Family Time!	Lesson 3. Is your family big or small? Family Time!
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<p>O‘quvchidan topshiriqda bo‘yagan rasmlarini ko‘rsatib ularning kimligini ingliz tilida aytib berishini so‘rang. Ehtimoliy javoblar: grandpa, mother, grandma, father, sister, brother.</p>	<p>O‘quvchi chizgan oila rasmiga qarab quyidagi savolni bering.</p> <p>Savol: Who is this? (Bu kim?) Ehtimoliy javoblar:</p> <p>This is my ... (mother, father, sister, brother, grandma, grandpa.)</p>	<p>O‘quvchi uyga vazifani bajarib bo‘lgandan so‘ng, “Is your family big or small?” (Sizning oilangiz kattami yoki kichikmi?) deb savol bering. Oila a‘zolarini sanab berishini so‘rang. (Sonlarni ingliz tilida aytishi kerak)</p> <p>Ehtimoliy javoblar: My family is big /small.</p>
<p>Lesson 2. How is the weather today? Family Time!</p> <p>O‘quvchidan u qanday ob-havoni yoqtirishini so‘rang. U ham sizdan qanday ob-havoni yoqtirishingizni ingliz tilida so‘rasin.</p> <p>Ehtimoliy dialog:</p> <p>What weather do you like? (Siz qanday ob-havoni yoqtirasiz?) I like (Men ... yoqtiraman) sunny (quyoshli) hot (issiq) warm (iliq) cold (sovuq) cool (salqin); rainy (yomg‘irli)</p>	<p>Lesson 3. What is the season? Family Time!</p> <p>O‘quvchidan u qaysi faslni yoqtirishini so‘rang. U ham sizdan qaysi faslni yoqtirishingizni ingliz tilida so‘rasin. Ehtimoliy dialog:</p> <p>What season do you like? (Qaysi faslni yoqtirasiz?) I like(Men ... yoqtiraman.) autumn (kuz); winter (qish); spring (bahor); summer (yoz);</p>	<p>Lesson 4. What can you see in the sky? Family Time!</p> <p>O‘quvchi yasagan qutichani ochib, undan osmonda nimani ko‘rish mumkinligini so‘rang. U ingliz tilida javob bersin. Ehtimoliy javoblar:</p> <p>sun (quyosh); cloud (bulut); moon (oy); star (yulduz); rainbow (kamalak); bird (qush);</p>

Besides above mentioned activities it is highly recommended to implement and use following types of activities in involving family members/guardians in language learning process with schoolchildren depending on the age and levels of learners:

- Storytime in the Target Language: Set aside time each day or week for family members to read or listen to stories in the target language. Choose age-appropriate books or stories that are interesting and engaging for everyone.

- Language Games and Puzzles: Play language games such as word searches, crossword puzzles, or memory games using vocabulary words in the target language. You can also create your own games tailored to the language learning goals of your family.

- **Movie Nights with Subtitles:** Watch movies or TV shows in the target language with subtitles in the same language or in your native language. Pause the video to discuss the plot, characters, and language used in the dialogue.

- **Language Exchange with Native Speakers:** Connect with native speakers of the target language through language exchange programs or online communities. Arrange virtual or in-person meetups for language practice and cultural exchange.

- **Family Language Challenges:** Set language learning challenges for the whole family, such as memorizing a certain number of vocabulary words each week, practicing speaking for a certain amount of time each day, or completing language learning tasks or exercises together.

- **Music and Sing-alongs:** Listen to music in the target language and sing along together. Look up the lyrics and discuss the meaning of the songs, as well as any new vocabulary or expressions.

- **Outdoor and Nature Activities:** Take advantage of outdoor and nature activities to practice language skills in real-life settings. Go on nature walks or hikes and describe the surroundings, identify plants and animals, or play language games related to the environment.

We believe that the help of family members and guardians is a crucial motivating factor for students. In these activities, students discuss, learn and play with their family members/guardians. These activities help students build a good relationship with their family members. Because family members' attitudes toward the target language and the language learning process significantly influence language acquisition [Vivian Cook, 2016]. Incorporating these family corner activities into the daily routine can create a supportive and immersive language learning environment for young child, fostering their language skills while spending quality time together as a family.

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